

Utemuratova M.P.

senior lecturer at the department of
«Finance and Business Analytics»,
Tashkent State University of Economics
Islam Karimov, 49, 100003 Tashkent, Uzbekistan

БУХГАЛТЕРСКИЙ УЧЕТ В СОВРЕМЕННЫХ УСЛОВИЯХ**Утемурагова М.П.**

старший преподаватель кафедры
«Финансы и бизнес-аналитика»,
Ташкентский государственный экономический университет
Ислам Каримов, 49, 100003 Ташкент, Узбекистан

Abstract

The article considers accounting in modern conditions. As you know, in modern conditions of economic development, a distinctive feature of the external environment is market uncertainty and increased competition, then there is a need to expand the amount of information used to make managerial decisions. To ensure the sustainable growth of the organization, the task of the manager is not just to calculate the possible profit and cost of products, based on the organization's own potential, but to determine and predict financial and economic activities, taking into account the parameters of the external environment. As a result, the question arises of the development and implementation of new approaches in the accounting system that can take into account the maximum possible number of factors that can influence the activities of the organization for the effective management of the organization and ensure a high level of competitiveness of products manufactured by organizations.

Аннотация

В статье рассмотрен бухгалтерский учет в современных условиях. Как известно, в современных условиях развития экономики, отличительной особенностью внешней среды является рыночная неопределенность и возрастание конкурентной борьбы, то возникает потребность в расширении объемов информации, используемой для принятия управленческих решений. Для обеспечения устойчивого роста организации, задача руководителя не просто рассчитать возможную прибыль и себестоимость выпускаемой продукции, исходя из собственного потенциала организации, а определить и спрогнозировать финансово-хозяйственную деятельность с учетом параметров внешней среды. Вследствие этого, возникает вопрос о разработке и внедрении новых подходов в системе бухгалтерского учета, которые смогут учесть максимально возможное число факторов, способных оказать влияние на деятельность организации для эффективного управления организацией и обеспечить высокий уровень конкурентоспособности продукции, производимой организациями.

Keywords: accounting, competitiveness, modern conditions, market uncertainty.

Ключевые слова: бухгалтерский учёт, конкурентоспособность, современные условия, рыночная неопределенность.

Introduction

It is known that enterprises are the main link of the economy of any individual society, and accordingly, they are important subjects of accounting, which is a management tool. Through enterprises, tangible and intangible goods are created, various works are performed, services are provided and they are delivered to consumers. Increasing the number of enterprises, their consolidation, expansion, development of cooperative activities is one of the important factors of increasing the size of the country's gross domestic product, providing employment and increasing the income of the population, improving the standard of living and well-being of people[1]. Accounting and reporting in enterprises requires compliance with specific criteria, procedures and requirements.

Theoretical aspects of research work.

Accounting is one of the economic sciences, and its theory teaches the technique, subject and method of organizing accounting. This science studies and summarizes the methods of accounting in the economic sectors and introduces its advanced methods[2]. At the same time, this science develops ways of introducing the advanced forms of accounting methods of other countries into the national economy networks and recommends to put them into practice[3][4].

Accounting mainly performs the following functions[5]:

- a) to monitor economic processes taking place in enterprises, organizations and institutions of national economic accounting branches;
- b) expressing the data obtained through observation in quantitative instructions;

c) record the results of monitoring the economic activities of the enterprise, organization, institution in special documents;

g) summarizing and grouping information reflected in special documents, establishing control over economic processes and influencing them.

The above functions of accounting are of great importance in drawing up economically based current and future plan indicators of some enterprises, institutions and organizations and the entire national economy, as well as in monitoring their implementation.

Accounting has 3 main tasks[6]:

1. Control over the implementation of the plan. In enterprise accounting, this task is defined as follows:

1.1. Product (work, service) production plan implementation, monitoring and control of the nomenclature, type, quality of the products specified in the plan, determining the growth factors of the plan implementation;

1.2. Calculating the cost of products, finding the factors to gradually reduce the cost;

1.3. Control of the fulfillment of profitability levels of enterprises.

1.4. Monitoring the implementation of the business-financial plan.

2. Calculating the cost of products, finding the factors to gradually reduce the cost;

3. Control of the fulfillment of profitability levels of enterprises.

3.1. Monitoring the implementation of the business-financial plan.

In order to achieve uniformity in accounting and reporting, to increase the reliability and timeliness of accounting and reporting information, the countries have state regulation of accounting and reporting.

Analyze and result of research work.

The Ministry of Finance is preparing a new version of the Law «On Accounting». The goal is to harmonize the accounting system with the current Tax Code, take into account the introduction of IFRS in the law and help improve the professionalism of accountants.

By 2024, a qualitatively new law should appear, which will take into account all the new accounting requirements [10].

First, in 2019, a new version of the Tax Code was adopted, according to which taxpayers, in addition to accounting, keep tax records. Those. these 2 types of accounting are separated. This is not reflected in the Accounting Law.

Secondly, according to No.4611 dated February 24, 2020, joint-stock companies, commercial banks, insurance organizations and legal entities - large taxpayers, starting from January 1, 2021, organize accounting, and starting from the results of 2021 - draw up financial statements based on IFRS.

Thirdly, No.4611 provides for the improvement of NAS and their harmonization with IFRS. The Ministry of Finance is cooperating on this issue with the IFRS Foundation and ADB. In particular, a unified National Financial Reporting Standard based on IFRS for small and medium-sized businesses is currently being developed.

Fourthly, the Law should include a rule on the publication of financial statements in the public domain on a resource specially created for this purpose. Our business is not accustomed to disclosing data, but over time it becomes necessary.

Fifth, Art. 25 of the Law, it contains requirements to submit quarterly reports. According to No.419 dated November 10, 2022, from January 1, 2023, is cancelled the requirement for accounting entities to submit quarterly financial statements to tax and statistical authorities.

Sixth, personnel issues require attention. The current version of the Law does not contain such concepts as “professional accountant”, “certified professional accountant”, “certified professional accountant”, etc.

Seventh, the number of companies providing outsourcing services in the field of accounting is growing from year to year. However, there are no norms in the current legislation establishing requirements for them, including:

regulating the quality control of such services;

establishing requirements for the qualifications of employees and compliance with the Code of Ethics for Professional Accountants[7];

eliminating the possibility of a conflict of interest.

Eighth, it is necessary to prescribe the activities of the Council for the Development of Accounting Methodology. It should become a bridge between accountants, tax consultants, auditors, on the one hand, and the Ministry of Finance, the Central Bank and other state regulatory bodies, on the other.

Methodological problems, first of all, should be discussed not in social networks, but in the Council. And this body should contribute to their prompt solution. For this to work effectively, the mechanisms of interaction must be prescribed in the Law.

In addition to the changes discussed above, it should also be noted about the Accounting Policy, where it is mandatory to issue an order for the organization[8]. The order stipulates the methodological, technical and organizational aspects of accounting. The accounting policy of the organization includes[9]:

a description of the accepted methods of accounting;

chart of accounts of the organization's accounting; the forms of primary documents and accounting registers used by the organization, if they differ from the standard ones;

regulation of the movement of primary documents and registers in the accounting of the organization.

When forming the accounting policy of the organization, it is necessary to proceed from: isolation of the accounting of the property and obligations of the organization from the property and obligations of other legal entities and individuals; business continuity of the organization; sequence of application of accounting policies; temporal certainty of the facts of economic activity.

Conclusion

Due to the fact that foreign and joint firms have appeared on the market of Uzbekistan, it is necessary to follow generally accepted accounting principles, which are divided into two categories:

principles of change (estimation), which determine the moment of reflection of the event in accounting and the amount recorded in accounting registers;

disclosure principles that describe the qualitative characteristics of the information to be contained in the financial statements.

According to the national accounting standard “Income from core business activities” these principles are enshrined as a conceptual basis for reporting. Accounting data and reporting compiled on their basis require audit confirmation, which is associated with three problems:

1. confirmation of the reliability of financial statements;
2. the role of the audit report in the financial statements;
3. the accuracy of reporting data, confirmed by the auditor's report. Each owner sets the criteria for the credibility of accounting data, however, foreign partners need the opinion of an expert auditor, who must confirm or refute the finality of these criteria, their justification.

Thus, the audit report allows users of financial statements with very different approaches of owners to accounting methodology to treat financial statements with sufficient confidence.

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